

Discrepancy-based Control of Particle Processes

Eric Otto^a, Jessica Behrens^{a,b}, Stefan Palis^{a,c}, Robert Dürr^b, Achim Kienle^{a,b}

^a*Automation/Modelling, Otto-von-Guericke-University Magdeburg, Universitätsplatz 2, 39106 Magdeburg, Germany*

^b*Process Synthesis and Process Dynamics, Max Planck Institute for Dynamics of Complex Technical Systems, Sandtorstrasse 1, 39106 Magdeburg, Germany*

^c*National Research University Moscow Power Engineering Institute, Krasnokazarmennaya Ulitsa, 14, 111250 Moscow, Russia*

Abstract

The production of goods in particulate form is important in many industries such as the chemical, pharmaceutical and food industry. For the subsequent use, specific particle properties determine the quality of the product. In order to ensure high quality and furthermore a constant production rate, process control methods can be applied. Here we present discrepancy-based control for a generic agglomeration process with additional particle breakage. The advantage of this control approach is the direct and simple control design using the nonlinear and infinite-dimensional system description as well as guaranteed stability for the chosen process variables. Two practically relevant scenarios are investigated. First, it is shown that control laws for two moments of the particle size distribution ensure the production of agglomerates with a constant Sauter mean diameter. Then, control laws for the production rate are designed. The resulting closed-loop behavior is investigated by means of dynamic simulation. It is shown that the control laws improve systems convergence speed for both set point tracking and disturbance rejection and achieve zero steady state error even under the occurrence of non-vanishing disturbances.

Keywords: discrepancy-based control, infinite-dimensional control, particle processes, agglomeration, PI-control, input-output-linearization

1. Introduction

Particle formation processes are important unit processes in manufacturing and are widely applied in chemical, pharmaceutical, agricultural and food industry (Bück and Tsotsas, 2016; Palzer, 2007). Examples of such processes are crystallization, granulation by layering growth or agglomeration. The common goal of these processes is to produce particles with well-defined properties, depending on their intended end use. For most industrial applications particle size or shape are key properties since they affect many important product features such as solubility, mechanical strength and flowability. Typically these product features vary from particle to particle, which raises the practical problem of keeping them within defined boundaries during production.

In the industrial context a variety of technical realizations exists for the above mentioned processes (Litster and Ennis, 2013; Bennett, 2002), however the production of crystals, granules and agglomerates has in common that the final particle property distributions strongly depend on a variety of process conditions (see e.g. Chekal et al. (2009)). For example the gas temperature in a fluidized bed granulator affects the particle porosity (Neugebauer et al., 2018) and the amount of binder in a pan granulation process has an influence on the size of the product agglomerates (Przywara et al., 2021). While these dependencies can be exploited for adjustment of the product proper-

ties, they also make the process prone to undesired disturbances. For these reasons process modeling and control of particle processes have been in the focus of research in the last decades (Litster and Ennis, 2013). Contributions include mathematical modeling of process dynamics (Heinrich et al., 2002; Peglow et al., 2007), especially the influence of process operation parameters (Neugebauer et al., 2018; Strenzke et al., 2020; Turchiuli et al., 2005; Ennis et al., 1991; Otto et al., 2021b), as well as contributions on advanced process control and automation. A major challenge for control is the process' inherent property distribution whose (nonlinear) dynamics can be represented by partial differential equations (PDEs) (Ramkrishna, 2000). These are generally difficult to handle by traditional control design methods due to their mathematical complexity. Regarding the control of such systems the approaches found in the literature are therefore often based on linearized process models Vesjola et al. (2020); Neugebauer et al. (2019, 2020) or optimal and model predictive control strategies (Bück et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2006; Glaser et al., 2009; Maksakov and Palis, 2021) incorporating the complex system dynamics. These approaches usually rely on discretized (finite-dimensional) process models and are therefore inexact due to approximation errors.

In Otto et al. (2021a) a discrete population balance was input-output-linearized by choosing suitable output functions. This control approach is the finite-dimensional

equivalent of the approach for PDEs presented in this contribution, which is called discrepancy-based control (DBC). DBC has been introduced in Palis and Kienle (2014) and was applied to different particle processes (Geyyer et al., 2017; Otto et al., 2021c) as well as mechanical systems (Golovin and Palis, 2020) since. It is based on a weaker notion of stability with respect to generalized distance measures, called discrepancies (Movtschan, 1960). The significant advantage of this approach is that it allows for stabilization of systems with respect to these measures, even when it is difficult or impossible to find control laws stabilizing the system state with respect to norms (Palis and Kienle, 2014). The challenge is to find suitable discrepancies such that the desired system or output behavior is achieved. In addition to the explicit proof of stability, the control laws are derived directly from the nonlinear and infinite-dimensional process model, avoiding approximation errors from discretization and linearization. Finally, the derivation and implementation of control laws requires little effort compared to optimization-based approaches.

From an industrial point of view, stable continuous process operation is advantageous compared to batch operation since it yields high rates of product with constant product quality. However, continuous plant operation is often difficult due to disturbances, affecting the yield and desired quality of the product. Furthermore, changes of the operating point might be necessary when a variation of product properties is desired. Therefore, the aim of this contribution is to design discrepancy-based control laws, for disturbance rejection and changes of set points. Here, we focus on control variables that represent both product quality and throughput. To this end we construct discrepancies from moments (Otto et al., 2021c,a; Palis and Kienle, 2014; Geyyer et al., 2017) and in contrast to previous contributions also from the net particle production rate. By controlling two moment-based discrepancies it is possible to ensure a constant Sauter mean diameter, which is an industrially important measure of product quality. By controlling the net production rate a constant throughput is achieved. Furthermore the control laws derived in this contribution incorporate additional integral action, ensuring zero steady state error even for non-vanishing disturbances. The performance of the DBC approach is demonstrated by application to a general particle formation process including particle agglomeration and breakage (see Palis and Kienle (2014) for application to a process with layering growth) where the particle volume is the property of interest. For this purpose, the process is modeled using the established population balance framework (Ramkrishna, 2000), which results in a nonlinear PDE with the particle volume as internal coordinate.

The outline of this article is as follows: In Sec. 2 the process model is presented, followed by a brief summary of DBC in Sec. 3. Performance of the presented control concept for the continuous agglomeration-breakage process is evaluated and discussed in Sec. 4. The article finishes with a short conclusion and outlook.

2. Process model

In order to describe a collective of particles with individual properties, the population balance modeling framework can be applied (Hulburt and Katz, 1964; Ramkrishna, 2000). Here, dynamics of the particle collective are modeled in terms of $n(t, \mathbf{x})$, which is the number density distribution function of particles at time t , where \mathbf{x} is a vector of external or internal coordinates. Since the focus of this contribution is on the particle size, the particle volume v is chosen as the only internal coordinate. Dynamics of a process with continuous particle feed and outlet as well as particle agglomeration and breakage can be represented by the following population balance

$$\frac{\partial n(t, v)}{\partial t} = \dot{n}_f(t, v) - \dot{n}_o(t, v) + \dot{n}_a(t, v) + \dot{n}_b(t, v), \quad (1)$$

where the right-hand-side describes internal and external particle fluxes and the left-hand-side describes the resulting particle accumulation. The presented model is the volume-continuous version of the discrete model presented in Otto et al. (2021a) and extends the model in Otto et al. (2021c) by a breakage term. Note that this model in its general form can account for a variety of process setups from different fields of application. In the following the right-hand-side terms are explored in detail.

The feed term $\dot{n}_f(t, v)$ is determined by the number flux of feed particles $N_f(t)$ and the feed particles' size distribution $q_{0,f}(v)$, which is normalized with respect to the total number of particles, i.e.

$$\dot{n}_f(t, v) = N_f(t)q_{0,f}(v). \quad (2)$$

While the latter is usually assumed to be constant, the former can be varied over time. In practice N_f is computed from the feed mass flux \dot{m}_f . For simplicity, the feed distribution is assumed to be given by a normalized Gaussian function

$$q_{0,f}(v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_f^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{(v - v_f)^2}{2\sigma_f^2}\right\} \quad (3)$$

Product classification with separation function $T(v)$ is given by

$$\dot{n}_o(t, v) = K(t)T(v)n(t, v), \quad (4)$$

where $K(t)$ is the adjustable withdrawal rate. The separation function $T^*(d)$, usually defined for the particle diameter d , is given by the cumulative Gaussian function

$$T^*(d) = \frac{1}{\sigma_s\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_0^\infty \exp\left\{-\frac{(d - d_s)^2}{\sigma_s^2}\right\} dd, \quad (5)$$

where d_s is the separation diameter and σ_s accounts for non-ideal separation. Under the assumption of spherical particle shape $T(v)$ is computed using $v = \pi/6 d^3$.

The agglomeration term is based on Smoluchowski's coagulation equation and formulated in Hulburt and Katz (1964) as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{n}_a(t, v) = & \frac{1}{2} \int_0^v \beta(t, u, v-u) n(t, u) n(t, v-u) du \\ & - \int_0^\infty \beta(t, v, u) n(t, v) n(t, u) du, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the first term on the right-hand-side accounts for the birth of particles of volume v by aggregation of parent particles of volumes u and $(v-u)$. The second term accounts for the death of the parent particles during this process. The function $\beta(t, u, v-u)$ is called agglomeration kernel and reflects the volume- and time-dependent frequency at which two particles aggregate. It is often assumed that it is separated into a time-dependent agglomeration efficiency $\beta_0(t)$ and a volume-dependent coalescence kernel $\beta^*(u, v)$ (Sastry, 1975). For most processes the coalescence kernel function depends on a variety of process conditions and is therefore notoriously difficult to model. Besides some mechanistically motivated kernel approaches (Ennis et al., 1991; Sastry, 1975; Adetayo and Ennis, 1997; Hounslow, 1998) heuristic approaches such as the Kapur kernel (Kapur, 1972)

$$\beta^*(t, u, v) = \frac{(uv)^a}{(u+v)^b} \quad (7)$$

are widely applied. With two degrees of freedom the Kapur kernel is a versatile option for modeling of agglomeration processes (Otto et al., 2021b; Peglow et al., 2007) and therefore used in this contribution.

The breakage term

$$\dot{n}_b(t, v) = \int_v^\infty b(v, u) S(u) n(t, u) du - S(v) n(t, v), \quad (8)$$

reflects the spontaneous fragmentation of a particle of volume u into particles of volume v . The first term of the right-hand-side represents birth of new particles while the second term represents death of particles due to breakage. Here, particles are selected for breakage by the selection function $S(v)$, which is also sometimes referred to as breakage rate. The breakage kernel $b(v, u)$ describes the probability density distribution of the fragments. For mass conservation the breakage kernel b must obey (Das et al., 2017)

$$\int_0^v vb(v, u) dv = u \quad \forall u > 0. \quad (9)$$

As the agglomeration kernel, the breakage kernel is usually difficult to model and different approaches are found in the literature (Wang et al., 2020). In this contribution we choose S to be constant and a generic power law for b :

$$b(v, u) = (\nu + 2) \left(\frac{v}{u}\right)^\nu u^{-1}. \quad (10)$$

It is worth mentioning, that the control design procedure is independent of the specific agglomeration and breakage kernels describing the nature of the process. This will become clear in Sec. 4 when the control laws are derived.

3. Discrepancy-based Control

3.1. General formulation

Discrepancy-based control is a control-design technique for PDEs based on the notion of stability with respect to two discrepancies. In the following the necessary definitions according to Palis and Kienle (2014) are presented.

Consider a dynamical system described by a PDE, its solution $\varphi(\cdot, t)$ and an equilibrium at zero $\varphi_0 = 0$. The generalized distance between the process $\varphi(\cdot, t)$ and the equilibrium φ_0 is described by the discrepancy $\rho(\varphi(\cdot, t), t)$ defined as follows (Movtschan, 1960; Martynjuk and Gutovski, 1979; Sirasetdinov, 1987).

Definition 1. Discrepancy (Sirasetdinov, 1987).

A discrepancy is a real valued functional $\rho = \rho[\varphi(\cdot, t), t]$ with the following properties

1. $\rho(\varphi, t) \geq 0$,
2. $\rho(0, t) = 0$,
3. for an arbitrary process $\varphi = \varphi(\cdot, t)$ the real valued functional $\rho(\varphi(\cdot, t), t)$ is continuous with respect to t .

Note that a discrepancy does not necessarily have the properties of a norm, such as definiteness. In particular a vanishing $\rho(\varphi, t) = 0$ does in general not imply $\varphi = 0$. The discrepancy can therefore be seen as a generalization of distance measures usually used in the context of infinite-dimensional systems such as the L_p - and the L_∞ - norm.

To account for deviations of the initial state $\varphi(\cdot, 0)$ from the equilibrium φ_0 , a second time independent discrepancy ρ_0 can be used. Here, both discrepancies ρ and ρ_0 have to satisfy a continuity condition at time $t = t_0$, i.e. for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and $t_0 > 0$ there exists a $\delta(\varepsilon, t_0) > 0$, such that from $\rho_0 \leq \delta(\varepsilon, t_0)$ it follows that $\rho < \varepsilon$.

Definition 2. Stability with respect to two discrepancies ρ and ρ_0 (Sirasetdinov, 1987).

The equilibrium $\varphi_0 = 0$ is stable in the sense of Lyapunov with respect to the two discrepancies ρ and ρ_0 for all $t \geq t_0$ if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and $t_0 \geq 0$ there exists a $\delta = \delta(\varepsilon, t_0) > 0$ such that for every process $\varphi(\cdot, t)$ with $\rho_0 < \delta(\varepsilon, t_0)$ it follows that $\rho < \varepsilon$ for all $t \geq t_0$. If in addition $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \rho = 0$, then the equilibrium φ_0 is called asymptotically stable in the sense of Lyapunov with respect to the two discrepancies ρ and ρ_0 .

Furthermore the notion of positive definiteness with respect to a discrepancy is introduced.

Definition 3. Positive definiteness with respect to a discrepancy ρ (Sirasetdinov, 1987)

A functional $V = V[\varphi, t]$ is positive definite with respect to a discrepancy ρ , if $V \geq 0$ and $V[0, t] = 0$ for all φ with $\rho(\varphi, t) < \infty$ and for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a $\delta = \delta(\varepsilon) > 0$, such that $V \geq \delta(\varepsilon)$ for all φ with $\rho[\varphi, t] \geq \varepsilon$.

A connection between (asymptotic) stability with respect to two discrepancies and the existence of an according Lyapunov functional V is provided by the following theorem.

Theorem 1. (Sirasetdinov, 1987)

The process φ with the equilibrium $\varphi_0 = 0$ is stable with respect to the two discrepancies ρ and ρ_0 if and only if there exists a functional $V = V[\varphi, t]$ positive definite with respect to the discrepancy ρ , continuous at time $t = t_0$ with respect to ρ_0 at $\rho_0 = 0$ and not increasing along the process φ , i.e. $\dot{V} \leq 0$. The process is asymptotically stable if in addition $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} V = 0$.

3.2. Choice of Discrepancies for Particle Formation Processes

Very often the goal of process control in the infinite-dimensional setting is to stabilize system states with respect to norms of the distributed state, e.g. the L_2 - or L_∞ -norm. This is however hardly possible in most cases and often not necessary from a process point of view. Discrepancy-based control offers a practicable alternative by allowing to stabilize measures that do not necessarily possess properties of a metric or norm. The advantage is that, by an appropriate choice of the discrepancies, specific (scalar or vector-valued) process variables of interest can be controlled. Furthermore, discrepancy-based controllers can also be stabilizing with respect to a norm, if the corresponding zero-dynamics are stable (Palis and Kienle, 2014), which, however, is generally difficult to proof.

For particle formation processes discrepancies derived from the moments

$$\mu_i(t) = \int_0^\infty v^i n(t, v) dv \quad (11)$$

of particle size distributions have been successfully utilized as controlled variables (Palis and Kienle, 2014; Otto et al., 2021c; Neugebauer et al., 2019; Vollmer and Raisch, 2006). The choice of moments depends on the specific process as well as the goals of control. Layering growth processes for example are known to exhibit self-sustained oscillations. By controlling the second moment (with respect to the diameter) these oscillations could be suppressed (Palis and Kienle, 2014). Furthermore some moments are interesting for process control purposes since they represent important process variables. For the class of particulate processes in this contribution important moments and derived quantities are the first moment and the Sauter mean diameter. The first moment of a volume-dependent number density

distribution equals the total bed volume, which should always be within defined boundaries to guarantee safe and reliable plant operation. The Sauter mean diameter d_{32} is an important quality measure for size-distributed particle collectives and is defined as the quotient of the total volume and the total particle surface. The latter is proportional to the 2/3th moment, i.e.:

$$d_{32} = \frac{1}{\pi(6/\pi)^{2/3}} \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_{2/3}}. \quad (12)$$

Controlling both moments is thus expected to improve the product quality. The associated control errors are defined as

$$e_1(t) = \mu_{1,d} - \mu_1(t), \quad (13)$$

$$e_{2/3}(t) = \mu_{2/3,d} - \mu_{2/3}(t), \quad (14)$$

where the desired steady state moment is characterized by the subscript 'd'. The choices

$$\rho_1(t) = \frac{1}{2} e_1^2, \quad (15)$$

$$\rho_{2/3}(t) = \frac{1}{2} e_{2/3}^2. \quad (16)$$

clearly satisfy the properties of discrepancies for continuous solutions $n(t, v)$. For simplicity, the additional time-independent discrepancies accounting for the initial state are simply chosen as $\rho_1(0)$ and $\rho_{2/3}(0)$, ensuring the continuity condition. In Sec. 4.2 these discrepancies will be utilized for designing stabilizing control laws for d_{32} .

In addition to the product quality, the throughput of a process system is an important issue from an industrial point of view, especially for continuously operated plants. For the present process the throughput of the plant can be defined as the net volume production rate

$$\dot{P}_V(t) = \int_{v_1}^{v_2} v (\dot{n}_a(t, v) + \dot{n}_b(t, v)) dv, \quad (17)$$

where (v_1, v_2) is the desired size interval for product particles. Here, \dot{P}_V represents the net volume of particles in the product size range, that is produced per unit of time, taking into account the birth and death of particles in that volume range due to agglomeration and breakage. The particle feed is not considered since it is assumed that no particles of product size are fed to the process. The according control error e_V and discrepancy $\rho_V(t)$ then are

$$e_V(t) = \dot{P}_{V,d} - \dot{P}_V(t) \quad (18)$$

$$\rho_V(t) = \frac{1}{2} e_V^2, \quad (19)$$

The time-independent discrepancy accounting for the initial condition is, once again, chosen as $\rho_V(0)$.

Note that if we additionally chose to control the net surface production rate

$$\dot{P}_A := \alpha \int_{v_1}^{v_2} v^{2/3} (\dot{n}_a(t, v) + \dot{n}_b(t, v)) dv, \quad (20)$$

where α denotes the appropriate form factor, we ensure that the net product of particles has the desired Sauter mean diameter.

4. Results

4.1. Simulation Scenarios

From a practical point of view, a continuous particle production process has to operate reliably in different situations and under a variety of external circumstances, which should be ensured by the controllers. The situations typically include the change of the set point (CSP), where the process is brought to a new desired set point from some initial state, and disturbance rejection, where the process is held at a given set point despite the influence of an external disturbance. Generally, the change of the set point and the return to the set point after a disturbance should happen as fast as possible with reasonable costs regarding the manipulated variables. Both operations should be robust with respect to unavoidable uncertainties in the process model.

As presented in the previous section, controllers for two variables, the Sauter mean diameter and the net volume production rate, are designed. They are tested for a change of the desired d_{32} from 1.05 mm to 1.21 mm and a step disturbance where 183 cm³ of feed particle material is introduced into and 546 cm³ of product particle material is removed from the process chamber instantaneously. The latter results in a 7%-change of the first and a 3.5%-change of the 3/3-th moment and particle size distribution shifted significantly towards smaller particles. These scenarios are simulated for the ideal case without, and for the realistic case with model-plant-mismatch (MPM). For the latter it is assumed that the value of the agglomeration efficiency β_0 is given to the controller with a 50%-error. An overview over the six simulation scenarios considered is given in Tab. 1. In order to test the discrepancy-based control laws the particle process presented in Sec. 2 is simulated in closed-loop with the controllers and compared to open-loop simulations. The simulation parameters for the particle agglomeration, feed and outlet are taken from Otto et al. (2021b). For the particle breakage a generic kernel and generic selection function parameters are chosen. The process parameters are summarized in Tab. 2. In order to

Table 1: Overview over simulation scenarios (CSP: change of set point; MPM: Model-plant-mismatch).

ID	control variable	Mode of operation	MPM
I	d_{32}	CSP	no
II	d_{32}	disturbance	no
III	d_{32}	CSP	yes
IV	d_{32}	disturbance	yes
V	\dot{P}_V	CSP	no
VI	\dot{P}_V	disturbance	no

Table 2: Plant, simulation and controller parameters.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Controller Tuning		
R	diag(3, 3)	
Q	diag(1×10^2 , 1×10^2 , 1×10^4)	
Controller (CSP)		
$c_{2/3}$	2.1×10^{-3} (8.5×10^{-3})	
c_1	6.3×10^{-4} (1.8×10^{-3})	
c_a	2×10^{-2}	
Controller (Disturbance)		
$c_{2/3}$		
c_1		
c_a	2×10^{-2}	
$\gamma_{2/3}$	3×10^{-7}	
γ_1	3×10^{-7}	
Set points		
$\mu_{2/3,d}$	11.15 \rightarrow 17.35	m ²
$\mu_{1,d}$	$5.67 \times 10^{-3} \rightarrow 1 \times 10^{-2}$	m ³
K_{nom}	$5 \times 10^{-4} \rightarrow 3.5 \times 10^{-4}$	s ⁻¹
$N_{f,\text{nom}}$	$3.5 \times 10^5 \rightarrow 5.25 \times 10^5$	s ⁻¹
Feed		
v_f	4.2×10^{-4}	mm ³
σ_f	0.1×10^{-4}	mm ³
Separation		
d_s	0.7	mm
σ_s	0.2	mm
Breakage		
ν	1.3	
S	1×10^5	s ⁻¹
Agglomeration		
β_0	9.9×10^{-17}	s ⁻¹
b	0.272	
a	0	
Product size range		
v_1	0.18	mm ³
v_2	0.9	mm ³

solve the model equation numerically it is discretized using the cell-average technique introduced by Kumar et al. (2008) resulting in a 100-dimensional system of ODEs.

4.2. Controller Design and Verification for the Sauter Diameter

In this subsection control laws for μ_1 and $\mu_{2/3}$ are derived, by using the discrepancies ρ_1 and $\rho_{2/3}$ as presented in Sec. 3. For clarity, the procedure is divided into two steps. At first, a controller for the 2/3-th moment is designed using the feed rate N_f as the manipulated variable. Then the control system is augmented by a second control-loop for the first moment using K as the manipulated variable. The pairing of controlled and manipulated variables is justified by the fact that the total volume (μ_1) of a particle size distribution is more sensitive to the addition or removal of large-sized particles and the total surface ($\mu_{2/3}$) is more sensitive to a change of the number of small-sized particle. Since the number of large-sized particles is mainly

Figure 1: Simulation scenario I: A change of the set point at $t = 10\text{min}$ is simulated. The figures present the convergence of the first (upper left) and the 2/3th (upper right) moment as well as the manipulated variables K (lower left) and N_f (lower right) in open-loop (black) and closed-loop operation (red). The discrepancy-based controller improves the time of convergence for the moments with reasonable values of the manipulated variables.

Figure 2: Simulation scenario I: Evolution of the Sauter mean diameter d_{32} . The desired steady is reached faster with control, however the initial deviation after the step is increased. Note that this deviation can be reduced by adapting the weighting matrix Q .

influenced by the withdrawal rate and the number of small-sized particles by the feed rate, these pairings are the best choice. The first Lyapunov functional is chosen as follows

$$V_{2/3} = \rho_{2/3} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} (n_d - n) dv \right)^2, \quad (21)$$

where n_d denotes the desired steady state particle size distribution. The time-derivative of V along the trajectories is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_{2/3} = & -e_{2/3} \left(N_f \int_0^\infty v^{2/3} q_{0,\text{feed}} dv \right. \\ & \left. + \int_0^\infty v^{2/3} (\dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - K T n) dv \right). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Choosing

$$\begin{aligned} N_f = & \left(\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} q_{0,\text{feed}} dv \right)^{-1} \left(c_{2/3} e_{2/3} \right. \\ & \left. - \int_0^\infty v^{2/3} (\dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - K T n) dv \right) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

with any positive constant $c_{2/3}$ yields

$$\dot{V}_{2/3} = -c_{2/3} e_{2/3}^2 = -2c_{2/3} V. \quad (24)$$

Therefore the controller asymptotically stabilizes $\mu_{2/3}$ and therefore the total surface of the particles. From the right-hand-side of Eq. (23) we see that the controller consists of a proportional part and a second part compensating the net change of $\mu_{2/3}$ due to nonlinear terms, resulting in an input-output linearized process such that

$$\dot{e}_{2/3} = -c_{2/3} e_{2/3}. \quad (25)$$

In order to simplify the following derivations, we rewrite Eq. (23) as

$$N_f = \psi(n) K + \omega(n), \quad (26)$$

with

$$\psi(n) := - \frac{\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} T n dv}{\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} q_{0,\text{feed}} dv} \quad (27)$$

and

$$\omega(n) := \frac{c_{2/3} e_{2/3} - \int_0^\infty v^{2/3} (\dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv}{\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} q_{0,\text{feed}} dv}. \quad (28)$$

For the second step the Lyapunov-functional

$$V_1 = \rho_1 \quad (29)$$

is chosen. By computing the time derivative and introducing the plant equations as well as the first control-law we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1 = & -e_1 \left[K \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f} \psi(n) - T n) dv \right. \\ & \left. + \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f} \omega(n) + \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

With

$$K = \left(\int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}\psi - Tn) dv \right)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} c_1 e_1 \\ - \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}\omega + \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

where c_1 is another positive tuning constant, we obtain

$$\dot{V}_1 = -c_1 e_1^2. \quad (32)$$

Therefore, the closed-loop system is asymptotically stable with respect to the discrepancies ρ_1 and $\rho_{2/3}$. By introducing both control laws into the process equation and computing the moments we obtain

$$\dot{e}_1 = -c_1 e_1 \quad (33)$$

Again we see that the closed-loop system is input-output linearized with respect to the error of μ_1 . Since both control laws incorporate both control errors we have a centralized MIMO-control approach, which achieves complete decoupling of the reference-output pairs as can be seen from Eq. (25) and (33).

In general, any pair of positive constants can be chosen for c_1 and $c_{2/3}$. In order to obtain a reasonable balance between minimization of the control errors and the energy of the control inputs, we numerically solve the following constrained optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} \min_c \quad & J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T e^\top Q e + u^\top R u dt \\ \text{s. t.} \quad & \dot{e} = F(n, u), \\ & u = G(n), \\ & n(0, v) = n_0, \\ & c > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

where $e = (e_{2,3} \ e_1 \ e_{d32})^\top$, $u = (N_f \ K)^\top$ and $c = (c_{2/3} \ c_1)^\top$ on the time interval $[0, 4h]$. Note that the error vector e contains both e_1 and $e_{2/3}$ but also e_{d32} which is defined as

$$e_{d32} = d_{32,d} - d_{32} \quad (35)$$

and reflects the deviation of the process from the desired Sauter mean diameter. The closed-loop dynamical equations $F(n, u)$ for the control errors e are obtained by computing the time derivative of e

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} -c_{2/3} e_{2/3} \\ -c_1 e_1 \\ -\frac{\dot{\mu}_1 \mu_{2/3} - \mu_1 \dot{\mu}_{2/3}}{\mu_{2/3}^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (36)$$

and introducing the definitions of the errors e and moments μ . The function $G(n)$ is given by the control law

Eqs. (23) and (31). The optimization is conducted numerically by using a sequential quadratic programming algorithm implemented in MATLAB relying on the built-in function `fmincon`. Due to the nonlinear dynamics of the process, the solutions of the optimization problem depends on the initial condition n_0 . Here we choose the initial distributions according to the simulation scenarios. In general this drawback can be overcome by conducting the optimization for the whole set of possible set points as initial conditions. This is however beyond the scope of this contribution, which focuses on the general control design procedure. The resulting parameters are presented in Tab. 2.

In the following, the results for simulation scenarios I and II are presented. For the former the control variables as well as the respective manipulated variables are presented in Fig. 1. The time of convergence is decreased significantly compared to the open-loop case. Additionally, the convergence of the Sauter diameter is presented in Fig. 2. We see that the time of convergence is decreased, while the initial deviation is increased. This deviation results from the different times of convergence of the two moments whose quotient is proportional to the d_{32} . By further increasing the convergence speed of the volume control loop, i.e. adapting the weighting matrix Q , the overshoot of the Sauter diameter can be reduced.

The results for the disturbance rejection (scenario II) are presented in Figs. 3 and 4. The closed-loop convergence rate of both, the moments and the Sauter diameter is clearly improved by the discrepancy-based controller. Furthermore, the manipulated variables are within reasonable boundaries.

4.3. Discrepancy-based control with integral action

For the model-plant-mismatch scenarios III and IV the control laws are modified. Since complete knowledge of process models is rarely available in practice, it is realistic to assume that only approximations of the plant parameters are known beforehand. The errors induced by wrong plant parameters can be interpreted as non-vanishing disturbances. From linear control theory it is well known that integral control action ensures zero steady-state error in the case of such disturbances. This idea is adopted for the present control system. In order to derive discrepancy-based controllers with integral part, the Lyapunov functionals are augmented in the following way

$$\tilde{V}_{2/3} = V_{2/3} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\gamma_{2/3} \int_0^t e_{2/3}(\tau) d\tau \right)^2, \quad (37)$$

Figure 3: Simulation scenario II: The figures present the convergence of the first (upper left) and the 2/3-th (upper right) moment as well as the manipulated variables K (lower left) and N_f (lower right) in open-loop (black) and closed-loop operation (red). The discrepancy-based controller improves the time of convergence for the moments with reasonable values of the manipulated variables.

Figure 4: Simulation scenario II: Evolution of the Sauter-diameter d_{32} . The desired steady is reached faster with control.

where $\gamma_{2/3}$ is an additional tuning parameter. Introducing the model equations into the time derivative yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{V}}_{2/3} &= e_{2/3} \left(\dot{e}_{2/3} + \gamma_{2/3} \int_0^t e_{2/3}(\tau) d\tau \right) \\ &= -e_{2/3} \left(\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} (N_f q_{0,\text{feed}} - KTn \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv - \gamma_{2/3} \int_0^t e_{2/3}(\tau) d\tau \right). \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

By choosing

$$\begin{aligned} N_f &= \left(\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} q_{0,\text{feed}} dv \right)^{-1} \left(c_{2/3} e_{2/3} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_{2/3} \int_0^t e_{2/3}(\tau) d\tau \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^\infty v^{2/3} (\dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - KTn) dv \right) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

we obtain

$$\dot{\tilde{V}}_{2/3} = -c_{2/3} e_{2/3}^2, \quad (40)$$

which is negative definite. From Eq. 39 we see that the controller performs proportional (first term in the numer-

ator) and integral control action (second term), as well as a compensation of plant nonlinearities (third term). Analogously, the control systems is extended to account for the additional control of μ_1 . Again we rewrite Eq. 39 as

$$N_f = \psi(n)K + \omega(n) + \chi(n), \quad (41)$$

with the additional variable

$$\chi(n) := \frac{\int_0^t e_{2/3}(\tau) d\tau}{\int_0^\infty v^{2/3} q_{0,\text{feed}} dv}. \quad (42)$$

Using

$$\tilde{V}_1 = V_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\gamma_1 \int_0^t e_1(\tau) d\tau \right)^2 \quad (43)$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\tilde{V}}_1 &= e_1 \left(\dot{e}_1 + \gamma_1 \int_0^t e_1(\tau) d\tau \right) \\ &= e_1 \left(-K \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}\psi + Tn) dv \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}(\omega + \chi) + \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_1 \int_0^t e_1 d\tau \right) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= e_1 \left(-K \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}\psi + Tn) dv \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}(\omega + \chi) + \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_1 \int_0^t e_1 d\tau \right) \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

by introducing the process equation as well as the control law from above (Eq. 39). With

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \left(\int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}\psi + Tn) dv \right)^{-1} \left(c_1 e_1 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^\infty v (q_{0,f}(\omega + \chi) + \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b) dv \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_1 \int_0^t e_1 d\tau \right) \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Figure 5: Simulation scenario III: A change of the set point with model-plant-mismatch is simulated. The figures show convergence of the first (upper left) and the 2/3th (upper right) moment as well as the manipulated variables K (lower left) and N_f (lower right) with additional integral control (red) and without additional integral control (red, dashed). The discrepancy-based controller with integral part ensures zero steady state error for the moments even without correct knowledge of the process parameters.

Figure 6: Simulation scenario III: Evolution of the Sauter-diameter d_{32} in the model-plant-mismatch case with additional integral control (red) and without (red, dashed).

we obtain

$$\dot{\tilde{V}}_1 = -c_1 e_1^2. \quad (47)$$

Therefore, the process is asymptotically stable with respect to μ_1 and $\mu_{2/3}$. The control law (46) contains proportional and integral parts and furthermore compensates plant nonlinearities and the effects of the surface control loop. With the parameters c_1 and γ_1 ($c_{2/3}$ and $\gamma_{2/3}$ respectively) the proportional and integral control action can be tuned independently.

The process with model-plant-mismatch and controllers (39) and (46) is simulated for scenarios III and IV. The results are presented in Figs. 5, 6, 7 and 8. In contrast to the controller without integral part, the controller with integral part is able to stabilize the moments at the desired values in both scenarios, therefore being robust with respect to this model uncertainty.

4.4. Controller Design and Verification for the Net Volume Production Rate

This subsection is concerned with controlling the net volume production rate \dot{P}_V using N_f . The feed rate is

chosen as the manipulated variable since it seems reasonable to support or inhibit particle agglomeration by increasing or decreasing the supply of primary particles.

The Lyapunov functional and its derivative are given by

$$V = \rho_V = \frac{1}{2} e_a^2, \quad (48)$$

$$\dot{V} = -e_a \left(\int_{v_1}^{v_2} v \frac{\partial (\dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b)}{\partial t} dv \right). \quad (49)$$

After some straightforward calculations we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} = & -e_a \left(N_f \int_{v_1}^{v_2} v [2\zeta(q_{0,f}, n) + \eta(q_{0,f})] dv \right. \\ & + \int_{v_1}^{v_2} v [2\zeta(n, \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - \dot{n}_o) \\ & \left. + \eta(n, \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - \dot{n}_o)] dv \right) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where we define ζ and η as

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(n, m) = & \frac{1}{2} \int_0^v \beta(t, u, v-u) n(t, u) m(t, v-u) du \\ & - \int_0^\infty \beta(t, v, u) n(t, v) m(t, u) du. \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

and

$$\eta(n) = \int_v^\infty b(v, u) S(u) n(t, u) du - S(v) n(t, v). \quad (52)$$

Figure 7: Simulation scenario IV: The disturbance scenario is simulated with model-plant-mismatch. The figures show convergence of the first (upper left) and the 2/3th (upper right) moment as well as the manipulated variables K (lower left) and N_f (lower right) with additional integral control (red) and without additional integral control (black). The discrepancy-based controller with integral part ensures zero steady state error for the moments even without correct knowledge of the process parameters.

Figure 8: Simulation scenario IV: Evolution of the Sauter-diameter d_{32} in the model-plant-mismatch case with additional integral control (red) and without (black).

From Eq. (50) we easily find

$$N_f = \left(\int_{v_1}^{v_2} v 2v \zeta(n, q_{0,f}) + v \eta(q_{0,f}) dv \right)^{-1} \left(c_a e_a - \int_{v_1}^{v_2} 2v \zeta(n, \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - \dot{n}_o) + v \eta(n, \dot{n}_a + \dot{n}_b - \dot{n}_o) dv \right) \quad (53)$$

to be an exponentially stabilizing control law since it results in

$$\dot{V} = -2c_a V. \quad (54)$$

The simulation results for the CSP case are presented in Fig. 9. The proposed control reduces the convergence time of the net volume production significantly with reasonable control effort. However, the convergence behavior of the Sauter mean diameter as a measure of product quality does not improve visibly. As mentioned in Sec. 3.2 an additional control loop for the net surface production rate would achieve simultaneous control of the Sauter diameter and the throughput. Augmentation of the control law

by an integral part for rejection of non-vanishing disturbances is easily possible analogously to moment control as presented in the previous subsection.

Finally the disturbance rejection ability is tested. The results are presented in Fig. 10. The undesired increase of the volume production rate due to the disturbance is counteracted by a reduction of the feed rate, resulting in improved convergence behavior for both \dot{P}_V and d_{32} .

4.5. Zero-dynamics and stability with respect to the L_∞ -norm

As mentioned before convergence with respect to discrepancies does not imply convergence with respect to a norm, i.e. stable zero dynamics. However, for nonlinear infinite-dimensional systems characterizing the zero-dynamics is difficult. In order to obtain an at least local finite-dimensional result, the discretized closed-loop control system can be linearized numerically. By computing the eigenvalues of the resulting system matrix stability of the zero dynamics (with respect to the discretized distribution) can be deduced. For the three control laws presented in the previous subsections the closed-loop eigenvalue with the largest real part lies in the left half-plane as presented in Fig. 11. Therefore the zero-dynamics of the discrete, linear systems are asymptotically stable in a region around the steady state and the particle size distributions converge point-wise to the steady state distribution presented in Fig. 12.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

Discrepancy-based control of continuous particle formation processes was presented in this contribution. To this end control laws have been derived for a generic process with particle agglomeration and breakage. It was

Figure 9: Simulation scenario V: The production rate (top) is controlled using the feed rate (middle). The time of convergence after the change of operation point is decreased significantly. The Sauter mean diameter (bottom) also converges although it is not the control variable.

shown that it is possible to control the Sauter mean diameter, which is an industrially relevant product quality characteristic and the net volume production rate representing the throughput of the process using only the feed and withdrawal rates as manipulated variables. For the Sauter mean diameter a MIMO control law was derived. By applying the DBC formalism asymptotic stability of the control variables during closed-loop operation could be shown analytically. The control law derivation was conducted directly using the nonlinear infinite-dimensional process, avoiding approximation errors from linearization and discretization and limiting the control design effort. A simulation study showed that the dynamical responses to a change of set point and to a disturbance are improved significantly compared to the open-loop operation. Furthermore the simulation studies revealed that the zero dynamics of the linearized and discretized systems are at least locally stable in all cases, i.e. the particle size distributions converge. By integrating additional integral control action zero steady state error could be achieved even with model-plant-mismatch.

Future research directions include the practical application of the control laws and further investigations regarding the stability of the zero-dynamics.

Figure 10: Simulation scenario VI: Convergence of the net volume production rate after a disturbance at $t = 10\text{min}$ (top) and the respective feed rate (middle) in open-loop (black) and closed-loop (red) operation. The disturbance response is improved significantly by the control. The Sauter mean diameter (bottom) also converges although it is not the control variable.

Acknowledgments

This work is funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) project "Center of Dynamic Systems". The financial support is hereby gratefully acknowledged.

References

- Adetayo, A.A., Ennis, B.J., 1997. Unifying approach to modeling granule coalescence mechanisms. *AIChE Journal* 43, 927–934.
- Bennett, R.C., 2002. 5 - Crystallizer selection and design, in: Myerson, A.S. (Ed.), *Handbook of Industrial Crystallization* (Second Edition). Second Edition ed.. Butterworth-Heinemann, Woburn, pp. 115–140.
- Bück, A., Palis, S., Tsotsas, E., 2015. Model-based control of particle properties in fluidised bed spray granulation. *Powder Technology* 270, 575–583.
- Bück, A., Tsotsas, E., 2016. Agglomeration, in: Caballero, B., Finglas, P.M., Toldrá, F. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Food and Health*. Academic Press, Oxford, pp. 73 – 81.
- Chekal, B.P., Campeta, A.M., Abramov, Y.A., Feeder, N., Glynn, P.P., McLaughlin, R.W., Meenan, P.A., Singer, R.A., 2009. The challenges of developing an API crystallization process for a complex polymorphic and highly solvating system. Part I. *Organic Process Research & Development* 13, 1327–1337.
- Das, N., Saha, J., Kumar, J., 2017. An application of semigroup theory to the pure fragmentation equation. *The Journal of Analysis* 28.

Figure 11: Eigenvalues with largest real part of the linearized closed-loop processes with moment P-control (cross), moment PI-control (dot) and volume production control (square). The eigenvalues are within the left complex half-plane, therefore the zero-dynamics of the discretized system are asymptotically stable.

Figure 12: Steady state normalized volume distribution of the process in closed-loop operation for all scenarios. The processes with control action reach the desired steady state with respect to the volume distribution.

Ennis, B.J., Tardos, G., Pfeffer, R., 1991. A microlevel-based characterization of granulation phenomena. *Powder Technology* 65, 257 – 272.

Geyyer, R., Dürr, R., Temmel, E., Li, T., Lorenz, H., Palis, S., Seidel-Morgenstern, A., Kienle, A., 2017. Control of continuous mixed-solution mixed-product removal crystallization processes. *Chemical Engineering & Technology* 40, 1362–1369.

Glaser, T., Sanders, C.F., Wang, F., Cameron, I.T., Litster, J.D., Poon, J.M.H., Ramachandran, R., Immanuel, C.D., Doyle, F.J., 2009. Model predictive control of continuous drum granulation. *Journal of Process Control* 19, 615–622.

Golovin, I., Palis, S., 2020. Modeling and discrepancy based control of underactuated large gantry cranes. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 53, 7783–7788.

Heinrich, S., Peglow, M., Ihlow, M., Henneberg, M., Mörl, L., 2002. Analysis of the start-up process in continuous fluidized bed spray granulation by population balance modelling. *Chemical Engineering Science* 57, 4369 – 4390.

Hounslow, M., 1998. The population balance as a tool for understanding particle rate processes. *KONA Powder and Particle Journal* 16, 179–193.

Hulburt, H., Katz, S., 1964. Some problems in particle technology: A statistical mechanical formulation. *Chemical Engineering Science* 19, 555 – 574.

Kapur, P., 1972. Kinetics of granulation by non-random coalescence mechanism. *Chemical Engineering Science* 27, 1863 – 1869.

Kumar, J., Peglow, M., Warnecke, G., Heinrich, S., 2008. The cell average technique for solving multi-dimensional aggregation population balance equations. *Computers & Chemical Engineering* 32, 1810–1830.

Litster, J., Ennis, B., 2013. *The Science and Engineering of Granulation Processes* (Particle Technology Series Book 15). Springer Netherlands.

Maksakov, A., Palis, S., 2021. Koopman-based data-driven control for continuous fluidized bed spray granulation with screen-mill-cycle. *Journal of Process Control* 103, 48–54.

Martynjuk, A., Gutovskii, R., 1979. Integral inequalities and stability

of motion [in Russian]. *Naukova Dumka*.

Movtschan, A., 1960. Stability of processes with respect to two measures [in Russian]. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics* 24, 988–1001.

Neugebauer, C., Bück, A., Kienle, A., 2020. Control of particle size and porosity in continuous fluidized-bed layering granulation processes. *Chemical Engineering & Technology* 43, 813–818.

Neugebauer, C., Bück, A., Palis, S., Mielke, L., Tsotsas, E., Kienle, A., 2018. Influence of thermal conditions on particle properties in fluidized bed layering granulation. *Processes* 6.

Neugebauer, C., Diez, E., Bück, A., Palis, S., Heinrich, S., Kienle, A., 2019. On the dynamics and control of continuous fluidized bed layering granulation with screen-mill-cycle. *Powder Technology* 354, 765 – 778.

Otto, E., Behrens, J., Duerr, R., Palis, S., Kienle, A., 2021a. Control of particle formation processes. *IFAC-PapersOnLine 11th IFAC Symposium on Advanced Control of Chemical Processes ADCHEM 2021*.

Otto, E., Dürr, R., Strenzke, G., Palis, S., Bück, A., Tsotsas, E., Kienle, A., 2021b. Kernel identification in continuous fluidized bed spray agglomeration from steady state data. *Advanced Powder Technology*.

Otto, E., Palis, S., Kienle, A., 2021c. Stabilization of Distributed Parameter Systems: Design Methods and Applications. Springer International Publishing. chapter Nonlinear Control of Continuous Fluidized Bed Spray Agglomeration Processes. pp. 73–87.

Palis, S., Kienle, A., 2014. Discrepancy based control of particulate processes. *Journal of Process Control* 24, 33–46.

Palzer, S., 2007. Chapter 13: Agglomeration of dehydrated consumer foods, in: Salman, A., Hounslow, M., Seville, J. (Eds.), *Granulation*. Elsevier Science B.V., volume 11 of *Handbook of Powder Technology*, pp. 591 – 671.

Peglow, M., Kumar, J., Hampel, R., Tsotsas, E., Heinrich, S., 2007. Towards a complete population balance model for fluidized-bed spray agglomeration. *Drying Technology* 25, 1321–1329.

Przywara, M., Dürr, R., Otto, E., Kienle, A., Antos, D., 2021. Influence of operating parameters on process behavior and product quality in fertilizer manufacturing using continuous hopper transfer pan granulation. doi:<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4889325>.

Ramkrishna, D., 2000. *Population Balances: Theory and Applications to Particulate Systems in Engineering*. Academic Press.

Sastry, K.V., 1975. Similarity size distribution of agglomerates during their growth by coalescence in granulation or green pelletization. *International Journal of Mineral Processing* 2, 187–203.

Sirasetdinov, T., 1987. Stability of systems with distributed parameters [in Russian].

Strenzke, G., Dürr, R., Bück, A., Tsotsas, E., 2020. Influence of operating parameters on process behavior and product quality in continuous spray fluidized bed agglomeration. *Powder Technology* 375, 210 – 220.

Turchiuli, C., Eloualia, Z., El Mansouri, N., Dumoulin, E., 2005. Fluidised bed agglomeration: Agglomerates shape and end-use properties. *Powder Technology* 157, 168 – 175.

Vesjolaja, L., Glemmestad, B., Lie, B., 2020. Double-loop control structure for rotary drum granulation loop. *Processes* 8.

Vollmer, U., Raisch, J., 2006. Control of batch crystallization—a system inversion approach. *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification* 45, 874–885. *Particulate Processes A Special Issue of Chemical Engineering and Processing*.

Wang, F., Ge, X., Balliu, N., Cameron, I., 2006. Optimal control and operation of drum granulation processes. *Chemical Engineering Science* 61, 257–267. *Advances in population balance modelling*.

Wang, L.G., Pradhan, S.U., Wassgren, C., Barrasso, D., Slade, D., Litster, J.D., 2020. A breakage kernel for use in population balance modelling of twin screw granulation. *Powder Technology* 363, 525–540.